

EFFECT OF ORGANIC FERTILIZER STANDARDS ON SOYBEAN PLANT PRODUCTIVITY AND SOIL FERTILITY

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ABSTRACT

The importance of organic fertilizers in increasing soil fertility is great. The article focuses on the significance of organic fertilizers in increasing soil fertility, and it examines the conditions for applying organic fertilizers to protect productivity, product quality indicators, and soil fertility. Leguminous plants are essential in addressing food shortages and protein issues, which require increasing their productivity by cultivating fertile land. The application of organic fertilizers increases soil fertility, enabling ecological product production. Consequently, a research study was conducted on gray-meadow soils irrigated since ancient times to assess the impact of applying organic fertilizers at different rates on soybean plant productivity and soil fertility.

The study results indicate that applying 20 tons of semi-rotted manure per hectare increased soybean plant productivity by 11 s/ha or 52.38% compared to the control option without fertilizer. Mathematical calculations also show that the grain yield obtained from soybean plants due to applying organic fertilizer norms is reliable. Additionally, the organic fertilizer norms led to an increase in the root and shoot residue of soybean plants, positively affecting soil fertility restoration by increasing the quantity of organic biological substances in the soil.

In conclusion, applying 20 tons of semi-rotted manure per hectare on gray-meadow soils that have been irrigated for a long time and lack nutrients can increase soybean plant productivity and maintain soil fertility.

Keywords: Soybean, legumes, soil fertility, organic fertilizer, productivity, root mass.

Introduction

In addition to satisfying the demand for food, animal feed, and industrial raw materials, maintaining soil fertility at an appropriate level and improving it to obtain a high, stable, and quality product at all times is considered one of the important problems facing agricultural science. Without protecting soil fertility, it is impossible to obtain high-quality products from agricultural plants.

Legumes are various botanical genera of the Fabaceae family. Soybean - **Glycine hispida** - is an annual cultivated plant belonging to the legume family **Fabaceae**. Soy is known as a valuable protein-oil plant in many countries around the world, and it is currently cultivated for various purposes in more than 90 countries. The largest cultivated areas are in the United States (about 35-40% of the world), Brazil (20%), Argentina (12%), China (12-13%), and India (8%). It occupies about 2% of the total area of soybean cultivation in Europe and 0.7-

1.0% in Russia. The world production of soybeans has reached 253 million tons, and the cultivated area is 100 million hectares. The average yield in the world is about 2.25 t/ha or 22.5 s/ha. The use of modern varieties (hybrids) and intensive technology in favorable conditions allows for the achievement of record soybean yields [9, c. 182-190].

In modern times, in the conditions of the rapid development of industry and intensification of agriculture on a global scale, the protection of natural complexes, separate ecosystems, including the soil cover, which is an important component of the biosphere and ecosystems, and fertility, which is its attribute, is relevant in the conditions of our republic, as well as throughout the world.

The purpose of the research

The main purpose of this research is to study the effect of applying organic fertilizer in an optimal rate on the growth and development of soybean plants, to increase grain yield and quality, and to protect soil fertility.

Scientific innovations

For the first time, the effect of optimizing organic fertilizer norms on the productivity of soybean plants, their quality indicators, and soil fertility in the conditions of the anciently irrigated Agjabadi region of the Karabakh region in gray-meadow soils poorly supplied with nutrients was studied on scientific grounds.

Methodology and scheme of the experiment

In the field experiment, 10 tons per hectare of organic fertilizer was applied to obtain an ecologically clean and safe product and increase soil fertility. 20 tons of manure and 20 tons of compost were also used.

To study the agrochemical characteristics of the area to be researched, soil samples from different layers were taken from the field according to the methodology, and agrochemical

analyses were carried out. The results of the agrochemical analyses of the soils taken from the experimental area are shown in the table below.

In the collected soil samples, total humus and nitrogen were determined by I.V. Tyurin, easily hydrolysable nitrogen by I.V. Tyurin and M.M. Kononova, total phosphorus by A.M. Mesheryakov, total potassium by Smith, absorbed ammonia by D.P. Konev, and nitrate nitrogen by the method of Grandwald-Lyage. Activated phosphorus was determined by B.P. Machig, and exchangeable potassium was determined by P.V. Pratasov [4, p. 5-24]. The results of the analyses show that the pH of the experimental soils is weakly alkaline.

As can be seen from the table, the amount of total humus varies from 0.65 to 2.41%. According to the classification adopted in the republic, the soil in that area is poorly supplied with humus [8, p. 1-8]. While the total nitrogen in the 0-20 cm layer of the soil was 0.11%, it was 0.03% in the 80-100 cm layer. The amount of nitrogen compounds assimilated by plants in the 0-100 cm soil layer was as follows: easily hydrolyzable nitrogen 16-51 mg/kg, absorbed ammonia 9.98-4.25 mg/kg, and nitrates 7.56-1.25 mg/kg, respectively. The amount of total phosphorus in the 0-100 cm soil layer fluctuated between 0.13% and 0.05%. The amount of activated phosphorus, which plays a major role in plant life, was determined to be 12.89-3.85 mg/kg. This suggests that the experimental soils are poorly supplied with phosphorus. The total potassium in the soil was found to be 2.51-1.63%, and exchangeable potassium was 275.2-74.5 mg/kg.

Based on the results of the analysis and the classification adopted for the republic, we conclude that the gray-grass soils in the Hindarkh municipality of Agjabadi district, where we conducted the research, are poorly supplied with the main nutrients. Therefore, it is necessary to apply a certain amount of organic and mineral fertilizers to crops in order to increase the effective fertility of the soil.

Agrochemical characteristics of the experimental field soil of Aghjabedi region (Hindarkh municipality).

Deepness (sm)	pH in water solution	Total nitrogen (%)	Nitrogen				phosphorus		potassium	
			Total (%)	Easily hydrolyzed	Absorbed ammonia	Nitrates	Total (%)	Activated	Total (%)	Reciprocal mg/kg in soil
0-20	7.2	2,41	0,11	51	9,98	7,56	0,13	12,89	2,51	275,2
20-40	7,5	1,78	0,10	42	8,45	6,74	0,11	9,52	2,12	211,3
40-60	7,7	1,34	0,08	3	7,19	5,61	0,08	8,64	1,85	132,1
60-80	7,8	1,12	0,05	25	6,01	3,10	0,06	6,11	1,71	96,7
80-100	8,1	0.65	0,03	16	4,25	1.25	0,05	3,85	1,63	74,5

The experiment was carried out from 2019 to 2022 in the Hindarkh municipality of the Agjabedi region in 5 variants and 4 repetitions on gray-grass soils that have been irrigated since ancient times. The "Alligator" soybean variety was used during the experiment, and organic fertilizers were added under the plow according to the methodology. The soybean sowing period was April 10-15. The results of the field experiments were calculated using the mathematical calculation method of B.A. Dospehov.

The accumulation of organic matter in the soil increases its absorption capacity, granulometric composition, aeration activity, microbiological processes, and the amount of carbon dioxide (CO₂) exported from the soil. This has a positive effect on increasing productivity [6, p. 241-249; 11, p. 25-36]. Research conducted by J.A. Aliyev, Z.I. Akbarov, and M.H. Nabiye

shows that under normal conditions, one soybean plant can form 25-30 or more tubers. Atmospheric nitrogen absorption and entry into the soybean plant mostly occurs during the phases of flowering, bean formation, and grain filling [3, p.31-40].

Nitrogen is one of the primary nutrients necessary for soybean growth and development, and soybean plants obtain nitrogen from several sources. These sources include 1) biological N₂-fixation by tuber bacteria, and 2) soil nitrogen. A high level of soil nitrogen inhibits symbiotic N₂-fixation, and under these conditions, the soil provides most of the plant's nitrogen needs [19, p.822-827; 20, p. 1–23]. To improve soil fertility and increase the productivity of cultivated agricultural plants, it is essential to develop and apply a scientifically based approach to alternating one-year grain legumes with other crops in the production of high-quality, ecologically safe products.

A soybean plant needs to absorb 260-300 kg of nitrogen to produce 30 centners of grain. Under favorable conditions, the soybean plant biologically fixes 200-220 kg of nitrogen from the soil air at the expense of fur bacteria living a symbiotic life in the root. The missing 60-80 kg is taken from the mineral nitrogen compounds in the solid phase of the soil through the root, and as a result, the soil becomes less depleted of nitrogen [3, p. 12-15]. Many factors influence soybean nitrogen fixation and response to applied nitrogen fertilizer, such as soil pH, temperature, and humidity [21, p.213-216].

The lack of the required amount of moisture in the soil has a significant impact on the physico-chemical and biological processes taking place in the soil, soil fertility, plant growth and development, productivity, assimilation of nutrients by plants, and other issues [14, p. 2157–2169].

Analysis and Discussions

Soybean has the highest demand for moisture during the mass flowering, pod formation and grain filling stages. Soybeans were watered at least 4 times during the growing season for normal plant development. Along with soil fertility, irrigation has a positive effect on the growth and development of plants to be planted, as well as on the course of biological, physical and chemical processes in the soil, and on the microclimate characteristics of the soil. During the study, phenological observations were made, and the effect of different organic fertilizer rates on the growth and development dynamics of the soybean plant under irrigation conditions was determined. Table 1 shows the effect of organic fertilizer norms on the height and growth dynamics of soybean plants.

As seen from the Table, the organic fertilizer rates had a substantial effect on the growth and development dynamics of the soybean plant. In the control variant without fertilizer, the length of the soybean plant was 15 cm during the branching period, 19 cm in the variant with 10 t/ha of manure, 18 cm when 10 t/ha of compost was applied, 25 cm when 20 t/ha of manure was applied, and 22 cm when 20 t/ha of compost.

Table 1. Effect of organic fertilizer rates on growth and growth dynamics of soybean plant.

s/s	Variant	Branching duration cm	Time of pod formation cm	Full ripening time cm	Growth in cm
1	Fertilizer-free control	15	51	70	-
2	Manure 10t/ha	19	58	76	6
3	Compost 10 t/ha	18	56	75	5
4	Manure 20t/ha	25	70	89	19
5	Compost 20 t/ha	22	68	85	15

Measurements were taken at the stage of bean formation, and the corresponding indicators changed as follows: in the no-fertilizer-control variant, the height of the soybean plant was 51 cm, while it was 58 cm in the variant with 10 t/ha of manure, 56 cm when 10 t/ha of compost was applied, 70 cm when 20 t/ha of manure was applied, and 68 cm when 20 tons of compost was applied per hectare. The height of the soybean plant during the full ripening period was also observed, and the results were as follows: 70 cm in the control option without fertilizer, 76 cm in the option with 10 t/ha of manure, 75 cm when 10 t/ha of compost was applied, 89 cm when 20 t/ha of manure was given, and 85 cm when 20 tons of compost was applied per hectare.

From the above, it can be concluded that applying 20t/ha of manure had a significant effect on the growth and development of soybean plants at different stages of development. Organic fertilizers provide the soil with the necessary nutrients for plant nutrition in agriculture, improve its physical and agrochemical properties, enrich the soil with beneficial microorganisms, slow down the rate of mineralization of mineral fertilizers in the soil, speed up nutrient uptake by the plant, prevent nutrient loss in the soil, enrich the soil with humus, provide trace elements, improve soil structure, keep the soil moist in the cultivated area, and have a positive effect on reducing the number of irrigations [15, p. 1–50].

Tmiryazev K.A. notes that irrigation and fertilization are closely related to each other, and effective application of fertilizers in irrigated lands remains the main factor in increasing productivity and soil fertility [9, p.182-190]. A seed planted in fertile soil, receiving plenty of sun and watered regularly and on time, will yield abundantly with high care and labor.

In the authors' study, it was emphasized that applying nitrogen before planting is beneficial for soybean growth, given that soybean plants do not form nodules at least 9 days after germination. In addition, initial nitrogen fertilizer can supply nitrogen until biological N₂ fixation by tubers begins [12, p. 312–323; 22, p. 234–237]. However, nitrogen fertilization at planting can reduce soybean N₂-fixation and yield. Therefore, the application of organic fertilizers can meet the plant's demand for nitrogen and other nutrients [13, p. 815–816].

G. B. Bodnor, G. T. Lavrenko, and others prove in their research that 170 kg of nitrogen, 40 kg of phosphorus, and 50 kg of potassium are required for the formation of 20 centners of grain per hectare at the Primorsk agricultural experiment station [10, p.11-15]. For a high soybean yield, it is necessary to use both biological N₂-fixation and nitrogen uptake by soybean roots [5, 6]. Applying organic fertilizer to soybean is based on the plant's nitrogen requirement during seedling development before the formation of punch bacteria, which is crucial for soybean growth and development [16, p.255-260; 17, pp. 497-533; 18, pp. 112-114].

Soybean fertilization is primarily related to soil moisture and the amount of atmospheric precipitation. Specifically, the efficiency of mineral fertilizers is more noticeable in rainy years. Studies show that the more moisture there is, the more effectively fertilizers dissolve in the soil into a form that can be absorbed by plants, and the better they are absorbed by the plant. When different types of fertilizers are used in years with little atmospheric precipitation, the increase in productivity is less noticeable [24, p. 2778–2787; 25, pp. 11-15].

The application of fertilizers at the optimal rate in plant nutrition is the main factor in increasing productivity. As a result of conducted research, it is known that it is possible to increase the productivity of soybeans if the soil is fertilized at the optimal rate and proportion. However, it should be noted that excessive fertilizer can have a negative effect on the quality of the product. After studying the grain yield and absolute weight of the soybean plant, we established the organic fertilizer norms for 2019-2022, which are presented in Table 2.

Table 5. Effect of organic fertilizer rates on soybean grain yield.

s/s	Variant	Yield (grain s/ha)	Growth s/ha		The weight of 1000 grains (gr)
			s/ha	%	
1	Fertilizer-free control	21	-	-	105
2	Manure 10t/ha	26	5	23,80	120
3	Compost 10 t/ha	24	3	14,28	116
4	Manure 20t/ha	32	11	52,38	168
5	Compost 20 t/ha	28	7	33,33	142

E=9,46

P=36,1

As can be seen from the table, the application of organic fertilizer rates had a substantial effect on soybean grain yield. Compared to the no-fertilizer-control option, the productivity of the soybean plant increased significantly in the options where organic fertilizer norms were applied.

The grain yield of the soybean plant in the no-fertilizer-control option was 21 s/ha, while it was 26 s/ha in the option with 10 t/ha of manure, 24 s/ha when 10 t/ha of compost was applied, and 32 s/ha when 20 t/ha of manure was applied. When 20 tons of compost were applied per hectare, the grain yield was 28 s/ha. The highest yield was obtained when 20 t/ha of manure was applied, which resulted in an increase of 11 s/ha or 52.38% compared to the control option without fertilizer. The increase in yield as a result of the application of organic fertilizer norms was found to be reliable based on mathematical calculations. The increase in yield was three or more times higher than the indicator E, s/ha.

Preservation of soil fertility is one of the most important issues in agriculture, as high and quality products cannot be obtained without maintaining soil fertility. Therefore, the correct and efficient use of arable land is crucial, and returning the nutrients taken from the soil with the agricultural plants planted every year is essential. This can only be achieved through the use of fertilizers, and the use of organic fertilizers is especially important.

The authors note that plant root residues play a critical role in increasing soil fertility as a source of organic matter. Plants that give more phytomass to the soil have the main role in the accumulation of organic matter in the soil. The amount of root residue a predecessor plant accumulates in the soil is of great importance in evaluating its effectiveness as a fertilizer. When agrotechnical methods are developed to normalize the mineralization of organic matter in the soil, the main focus is given to the studies conducted to determine the intensification of the decomposition of plant root residues in the soil.

It is worth noting that the variation in the amount of nutrients entered into the soil by root mass and tiller residues is related to the amount of plant residues and nutrients in them. Favorable conditions for efficient plant nutrition are created by a large amount of carbon dioxide, in addition to the nutrients that enter the soil with the plant root mass and remains of the stems. This, in turn, increases the productivity of agricultural plants and the quality of the product [7, p.15-20].

Root and stem residues restore soil fertility in agriculture. After the organic matter decomposes in the soil, it provides the plants with the necessary ash and nitrogenous nutrients. Root and stem residues improve the structure of the soil, and as a result of the accumulation of a large amount of nutrients, it increases the productivity of the following plants and the fertility of the soil [23, p.80-88].

Green manures are produced by planting legumes to maintain and increase fertility in Central Asian soils. From one hectare, up to 8 tons of root and root residues can be collected, which significantly increases the total humus and nitrogen in the soil.

Various scientists have studied the increase of organic matter in the soil due to the remains of roots and stems of individual plants.

The root system of plants senses all changes in the soil, and the formation and development of roots are primarily influenced by the density of the soil structure, its moisture capacity, and nutrients. Researchers, such as S. Kholes, G. Genzen, Y. Y. Sokolovski, P. Kossovich, V. G. Rotmisterov, A. P. Madestov, F. N. Mauer, V. I. Tsvinsky, and others, have been engaged in determining the distribution of roots in the soil. Z.M. Abdullayeva, K.M. Babayeva, A. A. Bektemiriv, Y. N. Mukhtarov, B. B. Zahidov, and other researchers have reported an increase in organic and agrochemical indicators of the soil due to the remains of roots and stems [1, pp. 17-20].

According to the calculations of many researchers, one centner of dry mass of cereal legumes accumulates more than 3 kilograms of biological nitrogen in the soil, as found in the research of V.S. Zaitsevin, R.A. Taghiyev, and A.D. Ibrahimov. The appropriate methodology determined that the stalk and root residues of soybean (93 s/ha) ensured the formation of 280 kg/ha of biological nitrogen in the soil [5. P. 17-25; 10, pp. 42-44].

Numerous studies and widespread production practices have shown that crop rotation with different root structures increases soil fertility. Based on the experiment conducted by researchers, it was determined that alfalfa collected 73.11 s/ha of air-dry weight at the depth of 0-50 cm of the soil. Multiplying this number by the coefficient of 0.18 determined by Popov, it is equal to 13.12 s/ha of biological humus. Therefore, plant residues form the basis of the formation of new humus in the soil, and due to this, soil fertility increases. According to the method of turning plant residues into biological humus (according to Muhammedjanov), in order to produce 1 ton of humus in the soil, it is necessary to bury 6 tons of plant residues in air dry weight. During the experiment, soybean collected 9.3 tons of aerial and root mass in air dry weight, and according to the mentioned methodology, this figure is equal to 1.55 t/ha of biological humus [2, p.65-66].

In addition to the above-mentioned scientists, in 2019-2022, we collected the remains of root stalks from the joint sowing of soybeans using the monolithic method, dried them in the open air, and weighed them. Total nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium in root and shoot residues were determined and listed in Table 3.

Table 3.3. Effect of application of organic fertilizer rates on root mass, chemical composition, and amount of nutrients of mixed crops.

	Root mass s/ha	Air dry matter in %			In kg per hectare			Biological humus s/ha
		N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	
Fertilizer-free control	17,3	0,74	0,16	0,69	12,80	2,71	11,93	3,11
Manure 10t/ha	21,1	0,81	0,18	0,72	17,09	3,79	15,19	3,79
Compost 10 t/ha	20,4	0,79	0,17	0,70	16,11	3,46	14,28	3,67
Manure 20t/ha	25,0	0,84	0,21	0,76	21,00	5,25	19,00	4,5
Compost 20 t/ha	23,9	0,82	0,19	0,74	19,59	4,54	17,68	4,3

As a result of the analysis, it was determined that the application of organic fertilizer norms has a significant effect on the mass of root and shoot residues of mixed crops. In the control

variant without fertilizer, the mass of roots and shoots was 17.3 s/ha. When 10 t/ha of manure was applied, it increased to 21.1 s/ha, while 10 t/ha of compost resulted in 20.4 s/ha. When 20 t/ha of manure was applied, the mass increased to 25.0 s/ha, and with 20 t/ha of compost, 23.9 s/ha of plant residues were collected.

During the chemical analysis of samples of plant residues, it was determined that the amount of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium changed significantly depending on the application of organic fertilizer norms. In the control option without fertilizer, total nitrogen was 0.74%, phosphorus 0.16%, and potassium 0.69%. However, when 10 t/ha of manure was applied, total nitrogen increased to 0.81%, phosphorus to 0.18%, and potassium to 0.72%. When 10 t/ha of compost was given, nitrogen was 0.79%, phosphorus 0.17%, and potassium 0.70%. When 20 t/ha of manure was applied, total nitrogen was 0.84%, phosphorus 0.21%, and potassium 0.76%. Finally, with 20 t/ha of compost, total nitrogen changed to 0.82%, phosphorus 0.19%, and potassium 0.74%. These positive features also had a significant effect on the amount of nutrients per hectare. In the control variant without fertilizer, nitrogen was 12.80 kg/ha, phosphorus was 2.71 kg/ha, and potassium was 11.93 kg/ha. When 10 t/ha of manure was applied, nitrogen increased to 17.09 kg/ha, phosphorus to 3.79 kg/ha, and potassium to 15.19 kg/ha. With 10 t/ha of compost, nitrogen was 16.11 kg/ha, phosphorus 3.46 kg/ha, and potassium 14.28 kg/ha. When 20 t/ha of manure was applied, nitrogen increased to 21.00 kg/ha, phosphorus to 5.25 kg/ha, and potassium to 19.00 kg/ha. Finally, with 20t/ha of compost, nitrogen was 19.59 kg/ha, phosphorus 4.54 kg/ha, and potassium 17.68 kg/ha.

During the study, the conversion of plant residues collected into biological nitrogen was determined. In the control variant without fertilizer, 3.11 s/ha per hectare was collected. In the case of biological humus formation, 3.79 s/ha was collected when 10 t/ha of manure was applied, and 3.67 s/ha when 10 t/ha of compost was applied. With 20 t/ha of manure, 4.5 s/ha was collected, and with 20t/ha of compost, 4.3 s/ha of biological humus was collected.

Conclusion

1. The plow and sub-plough layers of irrigated gray-meadow soils have low levels of main nutrients, indicating poor potential and effective fertility. Therefore, to increase the effective fertility of the soil, it is necessary to apply a certain amount of organic and mineral fertilizers to the crops.
2. In irrigated gray-meadow soils, the application of organic fertilizer manure at a rate of 20t/ha significantly improved the height and development of soybean plants at different stages of growth.
3. The highest yield was obtained when 20t/ha of manure was applied, resulting in an increase of 11 s/ha or 52.38% compared to the control without fertilizer. Mathematical calculations also showed that the grain yield obtained from soybean plants as a result of applying organic fertilizer norms was reliable.
4. In order to maintain and increase soil fertility, it is recommended to incorporate the root residues of leguminous plants into the soil. Applying organic fertilizer norms at an optimal rate significantly increases soil fertility by improving the structural, productivity, and quality indicators of soybeans, as well as having an effective effect on the residues of roots and stems. This confirms that soybean is a good predecessor for plants that are planted after it.

It is recommended to apply 20 tons of half-rotted manure per hectare to improve the structural indicators and increase the productivity of soybean plants in gray-meadow soils that are poorly supplied with nutrients.

Declarations

The manuscript has not been submitted to any other journal or conference.

Study Limitations

There are no limitations that could affect the results of the study.

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Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Ethical Standards

The research meets all ethical guidelines, including adherence to the legal requirements of the study country.

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